

PERCEIVED VALUE INFLUENCES LOYALTY THROUGH THE SATISFACTION MEDIATING VARIABLE OF SKI CUSTOMER IN CHINA

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Abstract

With the rapid development of China's ski industry, especially after Beijing's successful hosting of the 2022 Winter Olympics, skiing as an emerging leisure activity is favoured by more and more consumers. However, the development of the ski industry in China started late and has developed unevenly, facing challenges such as uneven quality of ski facilities and increasingly fierce competition in the market. In this context, how to enhance ski consumer satisfaction and loyalty, and thus promote the sustainable development of the ski industry, has become an important issue of concern to the industry and academia. This study aims to explore, through empirical analyses, how the perceived value of ski consumers influences customer loyalty through the mediating role of satisfaction, and to provide a theoretical basis and practical guidance for ski resorts to formulate effective marketing strategies in the midst of fierce market competition. A variety of research methods were used in this study, including interview method, literature analysis method, questionnaire survey method, focus group discussion, and data analysis method. By designing and distributing questionnaires, the study collected valid data samples of ski consumers from different ski resorts in China. Subsequently, the collected data were quantitatively analysed using SPSS and SmartPLS software. The study developed a theoretical model based on the relationship between perceived value, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, and verified the validity of this model through structural equation modelling. The results of the study show that the perceived value of ski consumers has a significant positive influence on both customer satisfaction and loyalty. Specifically, the higher the perceived value of ski consumers in the skiing experience, the higher their satisfaction with the ski resort, which in turn shows higher loyalty. In addition, customer satisfaction was found to play a partial mediating role between perceived value and customer loyalty, i.e., the perceived value of ski consumers not only directly influences customer loyalty, but also indirectly enhances customer loyalty to ski resorts by increasing customer satisfaction. This finding suggests that ski resorts should focus on enhancing the overall perceived value of consumers, such as improving the quality of ski facilities, optimising the service experience, and rationalising pricing, in order to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. Finally, the study constructed an influence model of "perceived value-satisfaction-loyalty". The model structure shows that the path from Customer Perceived Value to Customer Satisfaction is 0.481, indicating a positive and moderately strong relationship; The path from Customer Satisfaction to Customer Loyalty is 0.416, showing that satisfaction significantly influences loyalty; The direct path from Customer Perceived Value to Customer Loyalty is 0.350, indicating that perceived value has a direct influence on loyalty. The results of this study provide an important reference for ski resorts to develop effective marketing management strategies, which have high application value especially in improving customer loyalty. The study suggests that ski resorts should pay attention to the actual needs and personal experiences of customers, and accurately grasp the changes in customer needs and improve customer loyalty by constructing a 'perceived

value-satisfaction-loyalty' model. In addition, the study provides theoretical support and empirical evidence to promote the development of China's ski industry, and suggests that ski resorts should pay attention to all aspects of customer experience in order to improve market competitiveness and promote the sustainable development of the ski industry.

Keywords: Ski customer, Perceived value, Loyalty, Satisfaction, Ski resort.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2022, Beijing hosted the 24th Winter Olympic Games, marking the city as the first to host both the Summer and Winter Olympics (China Sports Daily, 2017). President Xi Jinping emphasized the significance of the Beijing Winter Olympics for boosting China's skiing industry (Zhao, 2018). Skiing, which began as a sport for Europe's upper class, has since become globally popular and economically significant. Rapid technological advances and supportive policies have spurred the development of China's ski tourism and related industries (General Administration of Sport of China, 2016). Notably, the "13th Five-Year Plan" and the "Ice and Snow Sports Development Plan" (2016-2025) aimed to engage 300 million people in snow sports and expand the industry to 1 trillion yuan by 2025 (Central People's Government of the People's Republic of China, 2016). By 2024-2025, China's ice and snow tourism market is expected to reach 340 million participants and drive a total output value of 2.92 trillion yuan (Wu, 2019). Despite its late start, China's ski industry is now developing rapidly (Liu, 2019). The Beijing Winter Olympics, along with strategies like "North Snow to the South," have accelerated domestic industry growth (Hao, 2018). Most studies focus on the industry from an enterprise perspective, with limited research on customer experiences (He, 2018). This study fills that gap by examining the relationships between ski customers' perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty, building on theories of marketing and consumer behavior (Dai, 2020). The findings will help ski resorts tailor strategies to enhance customer loyalty and improve competitiveness (Zhang, 2019). Studying customer satisfaction and loyalty, especially amid rising competition and uneven service quality, is crucial for the future growth of China's skiing industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Ski Industry

2.1.1 Ski Industry Overview

The global ski industry, particularly in Europe, the U.S., and Asia, is a significant economic driver. Switzerland, Austria, France, and the U.S. are leading players in ski tourism, with well-developed infrastructures and major equipment manufacturers (Dong, 2010; Yan, 2006). Despite challenges like climate change and economic slowdowns, skiing remains popular in these regions (Wang, 2010).

2.1.2 China's Ski Industry Growth

China's ski industry has grown rapidly, with ski trips increasing significantly since the 1990s. Although skiing participation in China is low compared to Western countries, the potential

market is vast (Tang, 2010). Recent developments, including artificial snow resorts and the integration of skiing with tourism and real estate, have contributed to the industry's expansion (Zhang, 2008).

2.1.3 Development Plan

Since the successful bid for the 2022 Winter Olympics, China has introduced policies to boost the ice and snow sports industry, including the "13th Five-Year Plan" and other strategic documents. These policies promote infrastructure development, youth engagement, and the integration of ice and snow sports with tourism and technology (Zhao, 2018). By 2025, the goal is to have 300 million participants in ice and snow sports, enhancing China's global influence in this field (General Office of CPC, 2019).

2.2 Customer loyalty

2.2.1 Definition of customer loyalty

Customer loyalty is a quantitative concept reflecting a customer's commitment to repeat purchases, indicating a preference for specific products or services. Initially defined through purchase behavior, customer loyalty includes resistance to market changes or promotional incentives from competitors. Loyal customers exhibit emotional recognition and satisfaction with a product or service, as well as a behavioral intention to repurchase (Zhang, 2016). Academic definitions of customer loyalty fall into three categories: behavioral, attitudinal, and integrative (Jacoby, 1978).

2.2.2 Customer Loyalty Based on Customer Behavior Theory

Behavioral customer loyalty is commonly measured by indicators such as purchase frequency and repeat purchase behavior. Early studies categorized customer loyalty based on repeat purchases, highlighting it as a key indicator (Brown, 1952; Lipstein, 1959; Kuehn, 1962). Researchers like Cunningham (1956) and Tucker (1964) argued that behavior, rather than customer psychology, best measures loyalty. Werbel (1973) expanded this concept to situations where customers disregard other brands, focusing only on their preferred one. Oppermann (1999) and Shao (2005) emphasized that tourist loyalty is more accurately assessed through behavioral loyalty.

2.2.3 Customer Loyalty Based on Customer Attitude Theory

Attitudinal loyalty is assessed through emotional indicators such as intention, awareness, and preference. Jacoby (1978) criticized behavioral loyalty, noting it might result from a lack of choices. Gremler and Brown (1996) and Zhang et al. (2004) argued that attitudinal factors, such as positive evaluations and preference for a brand, should be prioritized. Studies have indicated that emotional commitment plays a significant role in forming customer loyalty (Liu & Ma, 2003; Fyall et al., 2003).

2.2.4 Customer Loyalty Based on Integrative Theory (Behavior and Attitude)

This approach combines both behavioral actions and psychological attitudes to evaluate loyalty. Dick and Basu (1994) advocated for a holistic view, suggesting loyalty cannot be fully

understood by examining behavior or attitude alone. Oliver (1999) introduced customer commitment as a dimension of loyalty, while Ma et al. (2003) and Li et al. (2006) proposed that loyalty is the synergy between attitude and behavior, reflected in repeated purchases, emotional trust, and personal recommendations. Chen and Han (2020) also emphasized the importance of the behavioral manifestation of loyalty based on emotional bonds.

2.3 Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction, an essential marketing concept, indicates how well a product or service meets customer expectations. Initially applied to commodities, Cardozo (1965) introduced customer satisfaction in marketing, arguing that satisfied customers are likely to remain loyal. Howard (1969) defined satisfaction as a consumer's judgment of the fairness between what is given and received in a transaction. Hunt (1977) emphasized that satisfaction results from comparing expectations with actual outcomes. Similarly, Pizam (1978) linked tourist satisfaction to the comparison between expected and actual experiences at a destination.

Oliver (1981) posited that customer satisfaction stems from overall post-consumption attitudes. Woodruff (1997) highlighted that it arises from comparing a product's attributes and performance with customer expectations. Lv et al. (2000) reinforced that satisfaction is a cognitive response influenced by prior expectations and post-purchase perceptions. Hempel (1977) and Miller (1979) linked satisfaction to the degree of fulfillment of expectations. Woodruff (1983) added that it is an immediate evaluation, while Woodside and Daly (1989) considered it a consumer attitude formed after consumption. Bolton and Drew (1991) connected customer satisfaction to specific transactions and post-consumption evaluations, asserting that it strongly influences future purchases. Fornell (1992) and Kolter (1994) viewed satisfaction as a holistic attitude based on the difference between perceived functionality and expectations. Engel et al. (1995) argued that satisfaction depends on the consistency between pre-purchase beliefs and post-purchase performance. Li (2003) and Fu (2005) emphasized that satisfaction is a positive feeling generated when expectations align with actual perceptions of products, services, and environments.

2.4 Customer Perceived Value

The concept of customer-perceived value emerged in the mid-1980s, with Porter's idea that customers buy value, not just products, laying the foundation. Zeithaml (1988) defined customer-perceived value as the difference between perceived benefits and costs, emphasizing its subjective nature. Oliver (1988) linked this to equity theory, suggesting that customers assess value by comparing what they give and receive. Woodruff (1997) expanded on previous theories, stating that customers evaluate product attributes in specific consumption contexts. Sheth (1991) proposed five dimensions of value: emotional, functional, situational, social, and cognitive. Dong (1999) emphasized that perceived value differs among consumers, while Holbrook (1994, 1996) described it as an interactive, relativistic experience combining cognitive and affective aspects. Sweeney and Soutar (2001) identified four dimensions of value: emotional, social, quality, and price. They argued that improving perceived benefits and reducing consumer costs can enhance perceived value. Jing et al. (2001) developed a

mathematical model for perceived value, and Bai (2001) defined it as a trade-off between gain and loss. Patrick Fan (2003) and Zhong Kai (2013) emphasized the subjective nature of perceived value, noting that it varies due to individual differences.

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

3.1 Hypothesis on the relationship between customer perceived value and customer satisfaction

Many scholars have explored the relationship between customer perceived value and satisfaction. Oliver (1988) argued that customer perceived value directly affects satisfaction, while Ruyter (1997) studied its impact on museum satisfaction. Heskett (1994) found a bidirectional influence between perceived value and satisfaction in the service-profit chain model. McDougall (2000) confirmed a positive correlation between the two in service industries. Yang Long (2002) stated that satisfaction results from perceived value, and Dong (2004) highlighted customer tendency as a key factor. Feng (2008) provided empirical evidence in healthcare, supporting the positive link between perceived value and satisfaction. Overall, research has matured, confirming the positive relationship across various fields.

Hypothesis 1: Ski customer Perceived Value factor positively affect customer satisfaction.

3.2 Hypothesis on the relationship between customer perceived value and customer loyalty

Research indicates that customer perceived value significantly influences customer loyalty. Gale & Wood (1994) emphasized understanding customer needs to enhance satisfaction and loyalty. Frederick & Salter (1995) argued that influencing customer perception through policy can improve loyalty. Gronroos (1997) suggested promoting repurchase behavior by providing stable value. Sirohi (1998) linked perceived service quality to repurchase willingness. Fornell (2011) advocated increasing perceived value to build a loyal customer base. Kaesung (2013) highlighted perceived value's direct effect on behavioral intention, while Bo & Yin (2005) and Zheng & Weng (2014) confirmed its positive impact on customer loyalty.

Hypothesis 2: Ski customer Perceived Value factor positively affect customer loyalty.

3.3 Hypothesis on the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty

Most scholars agree that customer satisfaction affects customer loyalty. Anderson & Sullivan (1993) found a significant correlation between satisfaction and repurchase intention. Coyne (1999) suggested that loyalty depends on the level of satisfaction, and Woodside (1989) showed a strong link between patient satisfaction and hospital re-attendance. Gale (1994) emphasized the importance of perceived value over satisfaction in loyalty studies. Faullant (2012) noted the non-linear relationship between satisfaction and loyalty. Bai & Liao (2001) argued that improving satisfaction through perceived value leads to loyalty. Qi (2013) found satisfaction plays a partial mediating role in e-commerce, while Zhang (2016) confirmed the positive impact of experience marketing, perceived value, and loyalty in leisure resort hotels.

Hypothesis 3: Ski customer satisfaction factor positively affect customer loyalty.

3.4 Hypothesis on the relationship between customer perceived value, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty

Research on the relationship between "perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty" is well-established across various fields such as economics and tourism. Matzler (2007) found that emotional and quality factors, along with customer lifestyle and skill level, greatly influence satisfaction and loyalty in skiing. Dong (2004) supported the "perceived value dominance theory," asserting that perceived value is a primary driver of satisfaction and loyalty. Qi (2017) confirmed this chain in online travel, while Gallarza and Saura (2006) and Hernandez-Lobato et al. (2006) also verified the causal links in tourism. Chi et al. (2008) demonstrated that destination image directly impacts satisfaction, which subsequently affects loyalty.

Hypothesis 4: Ski customer Perceived Value Influences Customer Loyalty through the Customer Satisfaction

Scholars have widely explored the relationship between perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty in fields such as services, marketing, economics, and tourism. However, research in the sports field, especially on skiing consumers, remains limited. This study uses qualitative and quantitative methods to examine the perceived value-satisfaction-loyalty chain, focusing on skiing consumers. While prior research has established the "perceived value-satisfaction-loyalty" model, sports-related studies, particularly in skiing, need further exploration. Western research tends to use a mix of methods and is more comprehensive than Asian studies, which are often qualitative. This study aims to improve the research by integrating domestic and foreign scales and assessing satisfaction's mediating role between perceived value and loyalty in skiing.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Population and Sampling

According to the literature, ski customer loyalty in China is influenced by a variety of factors, including perceived customer value and customer satisfaction. Based on previous research, a questionnaire was developed.

According to the number of variables and influences in this study, the sample size should not be less than 180, and also, the researcher distributed 300 questionnaires considering the recovery rate and inefficiency of distributing the questionnaires. Data from 288 questionnaires were recovered with a 96 % recovery rate.

The researcher excluded samples with obvious problems such as the presence of unfilled, missing items, all options are 1 or 5, etc., a total of 19 samples were excluded, and 269 valid samples were retained, with a sample efficiency rate of 93.4 %. The information characteristics of the valid samples are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample data

Topic	Options	Frequency	Percent(%)
Gender	Female	139	51.7
	Male	130	48.3
	Total	269	100.0
Age	18-25	72	26.8
	26-35	67	24.9
	36-45	77	28.6
	Over 45	53	19.7
	Total	269	100.0
Skiing times	Less 1	67	24.9
	1-2	89	33.1
	3-4	79	29.4
	Over 5	34	12.6
	Total	269	100.0
Skiing level	Beginner skier	53	19.7
	Intermediate skier	133	49.4
	Advanced skier	83	30.9
	Total	269	100.0
Educational level	High school and below	58	21.6
	College	134	49.8
	Bachelor's Degree	62	23.0
	Master's degree	15	5.6
	Total	269	100.0
occupation	Students	33	12.3
	Civil Servants	39	14.5
	Teachers	36	13.4
	Doctor	24	8.9
	Entrepreneurs	30	11.2
	Business Executives	27	10.0
	Corporate Support	20	7.4

Topic	Options	Frequency	Percent(%)
	Freelancer	22	8.2
	Retirees	18	6.7
	Others	20	7.4
	Total	269	100.0
annual income	Less than 100,000 RMB	32	11.9
	100,000-300,000 RMB	62	23.0
	300,000-500,000 RMB	90	33.5
	500-700 thousand RMB	56	20.8
	Above 700,000 RMB	29	10.8
	Total	269	100.0

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Relevance analysis

In order to verify whether the variables involved in this study are correlated with each other, Pearson correlation analysis is used in this study. If it can pass the statistical significance test, it means that there is a significant correlation between the variables, which provides statistical basis for the next regression analysis.

The value of correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1. The closer the value of correlation coefficient is to 1, the stronger the positive correlation between the variables is, and conversely, the closer the value of correlation coefficient is to -1, the stronger the negative correlation between the variables.(Cohen, 2003)

Table 2: Relation analysis

	Customer Perceived Value	Customer Satisfaction	Customer Loyalty
Customer Perceived Value	1		
Customer Satisfaction	.475**	1	
Customer Loyalty	.540**	.571**	1

Note: ** stands for $P < 0.01$

Table 2 shows the correlation analysis table, Customer Perceived Value is significantly positively correlated with Customer Satisfaction ($r=0.475, P < 0.01$); Customer Perceived Value is significantly positively correlated with Customer Loyalty ($r=0.540, P < 0.01$); Customer Satisfaction is significantly positively correlated with Customer Loyalty ($r=0.571, P < 0.01$).

The above results of correlation analysis have preliminarily verified that the hypothesis is valid, but the correlation analysis can only prove the correlation between the variables, and cannot determine the causal relationship between the variables, therefore, when researching the relationship of the variables, after doing the correlation analysis, then further path analysis.

5.2 Structural equation model

Figure 2: Conceptual framework

As can be seen from the structural equation modelling diagrams: the path from Customer Perceived Value to Customer Satisfaction is 0.481, indicating a positive and moderately strong relationship; The path from Customer Satisfaction to Customer Loyalty is 0.416, showing that satisfaction significantly influences loyalty; The direct path from Customer Perceived Value to Customer Loyalty is 0.350, indicating that perceived value has a direct influence on loyalty.

Table 3: Path analysis

Hypothesis	Path	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
H1	Customer Perceived Value -> Customer Satisfaction	0.481	0.069	7.005	0.000	supported
H2	Customer Perceived Value -> Customer Loyalty	0.350	0.061	5.767	0.000	supported
H3	Customer Satisfaction -> Customer Loyalty	0.416	0.060	6.923	0.000	supported

Table 3 is the path analysis table, customer perceived value has a significant positive influence on customer satisfaction's ($\beta=0.481$, $P<0.001$), proving hypothesis H1: Ski customer perceived value factor has a significant positive influence on customer satisfaction's ($\beta=0.350$, $P<0.001$), proving hypothesis H2: Ski customer perceived value factor has a positive influence on customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction has a significant positive influence on customer loyalty ($\beta=0.416$, $P<0.001$), proving hypothesis H3: Ski Customer satisfaction factor has a significant positive influence on customer loyalty.

Table 4: Mediation effect test

	Estimate	Lower	Upper
Total effect	0.550	0.423	0.649
Direct effect	0.350	0.227	0.464
intermediary effect	0.200	0.127	0.286

Table 4 is the mediation effect test table, in order to verify the mediation effect more accurately, Bootstrap method is used, Bootstrap repeated sampling number is 5000 times, the confidence interval level is set at 95%, and the sampling method is the non-parametric percentile method with bias correction. As can be seen from the table, the total effect of Customer Perceived Value on Customer Loyalty is 0.550, and its confidence interval is [0.423, 0.649], which does not contain 0, indicating that the total effect exists. The direct effect was 0.350, and its confidence interval was [0.227, 0.464], which did not contain 0, indicating that a direct effect existed. The indirect effect is 0.200, and its confidence interval is [0.127, 0.286], which does not contain 0, indicating that the indirect effect exists, proving that hypothesis H4: Ski customer Perceived Value factor positively Influences Customer Loyalty through the Customer Satisfaction holds true.

5.3 Results of Hypothesis

Corresponding analyses of the impact of customer perceived value and customer satisfaction customer loyalty were conducted using Spss and SmartPLS data analysis software. Reliability and validity analyses, correlation analyses, structural equation modelling analyses and mediation effects analyses were conducted on the sample ontology and the hypotheses proposed in this paper were tested. The results are shown in the table below:

Table 5: Hypothesis test result

Hypothesis	Result
H1: Ski customer Perceived Value factor positively affect customer satisfaction.	supported
H2: Ski customer Perceived Value factor positively affect customer loyalty.	supported
H3: Ski customer satisfaction factor positively affect customer loyalty.	supported
H4: Ski customer Perceived Value Influences Customer Loyalty through the Customer Satisfaction.	supported

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 The influence of customer perceived value on satisfaction

Ski customers' perceived value is a subjective assessment of ski resort services and facilities (Sweeney, 2001). Research has shown that perceived value significantly influences customer satisfaction (Zeithaml, 1988) and that this influence is reflected in the three dimensions of function, experience and cost. Ski resorts should improve the perceived value of their customers by modernising their facilities, improving the quality of their services and offering a wide range of skiing activities (Petrick, 2002). Data analysis showed a significant positive correlation between perceived value and satisfaction ($r=0.475$, $p<0.01$).

6.2 The influence of customer perceived value on loyalty

Perceived value not only directly influences satisfaction, but also has a significant positive influence on loyalty (Fornell, 1992). Studies have shown that the higher the perceived value, the higher the customer loyalty ($r=0.540$, $p<0.01$). Customers with high perceived value are more inclined to repeat purchases and are less price sensitive, while forming a deeper emotional connection with the ski resort. Path analysis revealed a coefficient of influence of perceived value on loyalty of 0.350 ($p<0.001$).

6.3 The influence of customer satisfaction on loyalty

Customer satisfaction is a key factor influencing loyalty (Oliver, 1999). When customers are satisfied with the services and facilities of a ski resort, they are more likely to return and recommend it to others (Wang, 2010; Yu, 2022). Path analysis showed that the coefficient of influence of satisfaction on loyalty was 0.416 ($p<0.001$).

6.4 The mediating effect of perceived value on loyalty through satisfaction

Perceived value indirectly enhances loyalty by increasing customer satisfaction (Baron, 1986). Bootstrap analyses confirmed this mediating effect, with an indirect effect of perceived value through satisfaction of 0.200 and a total effect of 0.550, suggesting that ski resorts should focus on both perceived value and satisfaction to enhance customer loyalty.

7. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

7.1 An in-depth study of the multidimensional structure of perceived value and its influence on satisfaction

Perceived value contains functional value, experiential value and cost value, which significantly influence satisfaction. Future research should further refine these dimensions, explore the differential influence of different ski resorts and customer groups on each dimension, reveal how each factor influences satisfaction, and provide more targeted operational strategy recommendations for ski resorts.

7.2 Exploring the long-term dynamics of satisfaction and loyalty

Research has shown that satisfaction has a significant positive influence on loyalty. Future research could further explore the dynamics of this relationship over time, in particular whether there is 'satisfaction fatigue' after multiple skiing experiences. In addition, the influence of competition, price changes and fluctuations in the quality of ski resort services on the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty should also be investigated.

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